

Recommended citation: Kulcsár, N. (2020). Mathematics Self-Efficacy, Learning Approaches, Academic Performance in the Light of the Number of Failed Attempts. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 286-296). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14653789.

MATHEMATICS SELF-EFFICACY, LEARNING APPROACHES, ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN THE LIGHT OF THE NUMBER OF FAILED ATTEMPTS

Nárcisz Kulcsár
Széchenyi István University
Győr, Hungary

Conference Key Areas: *Mathematics in the engineering curriculum*

Keywords: *mathematics self-efficacy, learning approaches, achievement, number of failed attempts*

ABSTRACT

Mathematics is a language for expressing physical, chemical and engineering laws nevertheless engineering students often perform poorly in mathematics. Studying can be influenced by several different social, cognitive and non-cognitive factors which all can have an impact on students' academic performance. Many researches revealed positive effects of mathematics self-efficacy on mathematics achievement. Similar results can be found among learning approaches, students using deep-approach achieve better results. It is legitimate to question whether there is a relationship between self-efficacy and learning approaches.

My research focused on the interrelationship between two aspects of mathematics self-efficacy (mastery experience, physiological state), learning approaches (deep strategy, deep motive, surface strategy, surface motive) and achievement. This research also examined the variance of self-efficacy, learning approaches and achievement in relation to the number of failed attempts.

306 undergraduate engineering students at a Hungarian university took part in the study. To examine the above mentioned question the study employed quantitative approach and data were collected using two questionnaires during the semester. The self-efficacy scale was adapted from a variety of sources and was modified to local conditions. To measure learning approaches the Revised Two Factor Study Process Questionnaire was rephrased to the domain of mathematics and to the local conditions. The data were analysed quantitatively using descriptive statistics, bivariate correlation, partial correlation, and regression analysis. The results show that self-efficacy, learning approaches and academic achievement were strongly correlated with each other. Students who have higher level self-efficacy use deep strategy in learning and have deep motives, while students classified as low in self-efficacy adopted surface learning approaches. A new variable was introduced which has not been investigated yet in other researches: the number of failed attempts. A significant correlation between the mentioned variables and the number of attempts was identified.

My results demonstrate the importance of such kind of learning environment which fosters self-efficacy and deep learning approach.

1 INTRODUCTION

Numerous studies investigate factors that impact graduation and transfer rates in higher education but most of them focus on demographic factors. Amelink et al. [1] examined graduation from an other perspective and they found that college students who experience high self-efficacy are more likely to graduate and transfer. Cohen et al. [2] identified other factors as well, they suggest that rate of science and mathematics course completion, science and mathematics course enrollment, and required mathematics remediation coursework were significant predictors of graduation and transfer, namely taking mathematics and science coursework is positively related to successful outcome.

Mathematics is very important in the study of engineering but many students perform poorly in mathematics. There are many factors which can influence mathematics achievement: based on Marzano [3] meta-analysis 80 % of the variance in achievement could be accounted for by student effects, 13 % by teacher effects and 7 % by school effects [4]. This provides a strong reason for a deeper examination of student-related intraphysical factors including self-efficacy and learning approaches (deep strategy, deep motive, surface strategy, surface motive) and an other student-related factor – which has not been yet researched – such as the number of failed attempts.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Self-efficacy

The findings of Stankov et al. showed that a group of self-beliefs constructs, in particular, self-efficacy in PISA, confidence in TIMSS, and educational aspiration, in both TIMSS and PISA, were the best predictors of individual-level student achievement in mathematics [5]. The concept of self-efficacy was originally introduced by Albert Bandura as part of the social cognitive theory [6]. Self-efficacy can be examined in all areas of life but in this study education is in focus. Academic self-efficacy refers to students' beliefs about themselves and their academic competence influences their academic performance and level of engagement in learning and help determine what they do with the knowledge and skills they possess. Bandura [7] hypothesized that self-efficacy produces different effects through four major sources: mastery experience, vicarious experience, social persuasions, physiological states. The most powerful source is mastery experience that students gain during a learning process as they interpret their academic competence when they accomplish an academic task. Personal experiences with success and failure form students' perception about their ability to complete a task. The second source appears as vicarious experience. Observing others' experiences can empower students to believe in their own ability and success. The third source of self-efficacy comes from social persuasions, through feedback from peers, teachers, family. Finally, the fourth source is based on the physiological states such as stress, anxiety, fatigue and mood. These sources obviously contribute to students' decisions, how much effort they put in studying. Although all four sources examine one part of self-efficacy, but not with the

same weight. Hutchison et al. [8] implemented a qualitative measure of first year engineering students' self-efficacy beliefs and their results presented the majority of mastery experiences.

Previous researches report the variance of self-efficacy in the context of gender, grade level, age, achievement, different domains, migration background. However, self-efficacy is not independent from other intrapsychological concepts, researches investigate its interrelationship with e.g. goal orientation, self beliefs, confidence and learning approaches.

2.2 Learning approaches

Learning approaches has been investigated since 1970's, when Marton and Saljo, two phenomenological psychologists, postulated surface and deep level learning processing. This dichotomized view was extended by Biggs [9] who proposed surface, deep and achieving approach to learning all with two components, motive (why the student wants to approach the task) and strategy (how the student approaches it). A number of studies showed that a two factor model with deep and surface approaches has the best fit, instead of the three factor model. Table 1 provides an overview of the definition of learning approaches and its components.

Table 1. Learning approaches

Learning approach	Learning Motive	Learning Strategy
Surface Approach	meet requirements minimally: balance between working too hard and failing	reproductive: reproduce through rote learning
Deep Approach	intrinsic interest: develop competence in particular academic subjects	meaningful: read widely, searching for analogies, interrelate with previous relevant knowledge

The European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI) published A Framework for Mathematics Curricula in Engineering Education which aims to provide guidelines for universities and educators in the topic of general mathematical competencies for engineers, content-related competencies, knowledge and skills, teaching and learning environments, and assessment. A chapter is dedicated to attitudes, in which we can read about learning approaches and a possible path to a deep learning strategy [10]. Before any educational intervention, a state measurement is needed to set clear goals.

3 OBJECTIVE

The purpose of the present study is to reveal the relationship between students' mathematics self-efficacy, learning approaches and academic achievement in a new context by introducing a new variable (the number of failed attempts). Therefore, the present study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the preferred learning approach toward mathematics of engineering students taking the course Mathematics 1 or Mathematics 2 at Széchenyi István University?
2. Is there a significant interrelationship among mathematics self-efficacy, learning approaches and academic achievement?
3. How the number of failed attempts relates to the listed variables?

4 METHODOLOGY

4.1 Participants

This study was part of a larger multiphase research which examined students' learning characteristics and teaching method preferences in a Hungarian technical university. The participants of this study were 306 engineering students who participated in Mathematics 1 or Mathematics 2 courses in the same semester. Mathematics 1 and Mathematics 2 are successive courses in the first year at Bachelor level, and all students have to attend both courses. 36% of students have repeated the course at least once. Most of the students were mechanical engineering students (61%), but there were vehicle engineers, logistic engineers, computer science engineers, architects, and environmental engineers. Students completed two questionnaires right before writing the first mid-term test in October 2019 and second mid-term test in November 2019.

4.2 Survey instruments

The data collection instruments that were used: mathematics self-efficacy scale, study process questionnaire, university records.

2.2.1 Mathematics self-efficacy scale

The mathematics self-efficacy scale was a 5-point Likert type mathematics specific scale. The scale was comprised of 15 items which were adapted from a variety of sources and were modified to local conditions. Since mastery experience is the strongest and consistent predictor of self-efficacy [11], 11 items assessed this source of self-efficacy. Moreover 4 items aimed to measure the emotional and physiological states of students. One item in mastery experience and each of the physiological state items were reverse worded. The maximum possible score for self-efficacy was 75 (55 for mastery experience, 20 for physiological state) and the minimum score was 15 (11 for mastery experience, 4 for physiological state). The reliability coefficient (internal consistency) of Cronbach alpha was .89 for mastery experience and .77 for physiological state.

2.2.2 Study process questionnaire

The Revised Two Factor Study Process Questionnaire was adapted to the local conditions. The original 5-point Likert type questionnaire consists of 20 items. It measures two approaches: deep and surface approaches. Both approaches contain two subscales: motive and strategy. Each subscales (deep motive, deep

strategy, surface motive, surface strategy) have 5 items. These statements were rephrased based on local mathematics education for engineers. Some examples for rephrasing:

“I find that studying mathematics can be just as exciting as other engineering subjects.” (Original sentence was: I find that studying (academic) topics can at times be as exciting as a good novel or movie.)

“I spend a lot of my free time finding out more about the mathematics background of engineering classes.” (Original sentence was: I spend a lot of my free time finding out more about interesting topics which have been discussed in different classes.)

Cronbach’s alpha coefficient was used to examine internal consistency among items, .873 for deep approach, and .737 for surface approach.

2.2.3 University records

In this study academic achievement was measured by the sum of the two mid-term tests scores. The maximum possible score for each mid-term test was 12, consequently the total maximum score was 24.

The number of attempts means how many times a student registered for the same course because he failed to pass.

4.3 Method of Data Analysis

The data were analysed quantitatively using descriptive statistics involving mean and standard deviation, frequency distribution and percentage, bivariate correlation, partial correlation, and regression analysis by using the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS version 26). Mean and standard deviation were used to see the variation among the variables. Correlation revealed the interrelationship between self-efficacy, learning approaches and academic achievement. Partial correlation was employed to see the relationship between the listed variables while controlling the effect of the number of attempts. Regression was performed to see the independent contributions of the predictor variables to the criterion variable (academic achievement).

5 RESULTS

The purpose of the present study was to examine the interrelationship between students’ mathematics self-efficacy, learning approaches and academic achievement, and their relationship to the number of failed attempts.

5.1 Preferred learning approach

The data in Table 2 below present descriptive statistics of variables.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Deep Approach	260	10	50	30.32	8.038
Surface Approach	260	10	44	26.42	6.649
Mastery experience	256	13	55	37.94	8.563
Physiological state	256	4	20	9.63	4.009
Academic achievement	306	0	24	9.15	6.000
Valid N (listwise)	219				

Table 2 indicates that the most preferred learning approach was deep approach (M=30.32). The plot in Figure 1 gives information about that most students belong to a group with high scores in deep approach and moderate scores in surface approach.

Fig. 1. Scatter Plot of Study Approaches

More detailed analysis was conducted with cross tabulation. The numerical distribution in Table 3 supports the above mentioned results. Most students are classified as having moderate to high deep learning approach and moderate surface approach (43,84%).

Table 3. Cross Tabulation of Deep and Surface Learning Approaches Scores

		Deep Approach Scores				Total
		10-19 (low)	20-29 (moderate)	30-39 (high)	40-50 (very high)	
Surface Approach Scores	10-19 (low)	4	4	23	11	42
	20-29 (moderate)	7	52	62	14	135
	30-39 (high)	11	30	29	3	73
	40-50 (very high)	6	1	1	2	10
	Total	28	87	115	30	260

5.2 Interrelationship among mathematics self-efficacy, learning approaches and academic achievement

To reveal the interrelationship between the variables an analysis of the correlation coefficients was used. Figure 2 presents the bivariate correlations of mathematics self-efficacy (mastery experience, physiological state), learning approaches (deep and surface approach with the subscales), and academic achievement. There was statistically significant interrelationship between all examined variables except for surface approach where no significant correlation with achievement was observed.

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Fig. 2. Correlation among variables

A significant predicative correlation of deep approach, mastery experience and physiological state have been recorded on academic achievement. The deep learning approach explains only 4,7 %, the physiological state explains 3,5 %, while mastery experience explains 13% of the variability of academic achievement. This means that the more deeply students understand the material, the better their achievement is. As well as the more positively students evaluate the level of their acquired knowledge, skills and competences, the higher their academic achievement is. Furthermore, the more stressful a course is for students, the lower their academic achievement is. Moreover the reverse causality effects also work. The better students perform, the more students are motivated intrinsically/ the better students believe in their own abilities/ the less anxiety they experience. In summary mastery experience and deep approach have positive effects on later achievement and achievement is a source of

later mastery experience and deep approach. Furthermore physiological state has negative effects on later achievement and achievement is a source of later physiological state.

5.3 A new variable: the number of failed attempts

Several possible variables can influence the relationship between self-efficacy and achievement. Possible mediating or moderating variables can include but not limited to students' homework behaviour, motivation, engagement, perceived difficulty of the domain, effort regulation, goal orientation, personality, past performance, self-regulatory learning strategies, parental support, emotional intelligence, time spent on task.

Numerous researches examine the change of self-efficacy over time with longitudinal and cross-sectional sampling. Time appears in these researches as grade level but time can appear in other context as well such as how many semesters a student needs to accomplish a course. Since mathematics courses in higher education have a high failure rate, repetition of the subject may change the student's perception of their own competencies and may even lead to other learning strategies for success. These led us to investigate the relationship between self-efficacy, learning approaches and the number of failed attempts. There is a lack of research which would reveal the effect of the number of attempts. Table 5 presents the bivariate correlations of mathematics self-efficacy (mastery experience, physiological state), learning approaches (deep and surface), academic achievement with the number of attempts. Data show that there is a significant correlation between all variables which show that the number of attempts is a crucial variable. It should be emphasized that there is a negative correlation between mastery experience and the number of attempts, deep learning approach and the number of attempts, as well as achievement and the number of attempts.

In other words, the more times students fail the course the less they feel they have mastery experience, and the higher the level of arousal they have. Moreover, the more times students fail the course the less they use a deep approach to learning, and the more they use a surface approach. Furthermore, the number of attempts has negative impact on achievement.

Table 5. Correlation matrix among variables

Correlations					
	Mastery experience	Physiological state	Deep Approach	Surface Approach	Achievement
Number of attempts	-.285**	.211**	-.311**	.132*	-.138*

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

If we want a pure measure of the interrelationship between self-efficacy, learning approaches and academic achievement we need to take account of the influence of

the number of attempts. In this case, the results of partial correlations show that there is no significant correlation between any of the variables. Consequently there is no significant relationship between self-efficacy, learning approaches and academic achievement controlling the number of attempts.

5.4 Limitations

In this sample, there are students who failed several times in mathematics or in other subjects than it is allowed, so they had to finish their university studies. However, the following year they were able to reapply to the university and continue their studies. In these cases, we do not have information about that how many times they have failed in mathematics before.

6 SUMMARY

The present study reveals that the deep learning approach was dominant among engineering students which supports the findings of research by Hussin et al. [12]. This result suggests that engineering students are aware that to understand a mathematical concept deeply contributes to their academic success and professional life.

Significant correlation was found between all examined variables except between surface approach and academic achievement. Our findings confirm the conclusions of research performed by Veresová et al. [13].

The hypothesis that academic self-efficacy influences academic achievement was confirmed by numerous other researchers [14]. In our case mastery experience was the strongest predictor of achievement.

Our research is a niche in the context of examining the relationship between the number of attempts and learning approaches and self-efficacy. There has been a significant correlation between the mentioned variables. These results confirmed that the number of attempts is a significant variable, which can affect students' self-efficacy, learning approaches and achievement through persistence, desperation, coping strategy and self-confidence as the number of attempts increases.

Failing mathematics courses can prevent students from advancing in their other university courses and may impact their experiences about university, about their learning ability and negatively change their attitude toward learning. Mathematics courses appear as stepping-stones to understand the background of other sciences and to seek deeper in the field of engineering. Academic self-efficacy and learning approaches have been identified as crucial concepts when considering success and drop-out in higher education among underrepresented groups in STEM fields. The above discussed results capture a state in which educators have to intervene actively. Several "what to do" and "what to say" strategies for improving self-efficacy and motivation are listed in Margolis and McCabe's article [15] in order to help struggling students develop a more positive attitude. Problem-based learning seems to be a possible solution to enhance active learning and studies show that PBL enhances deep learning through discussing professionally relevant problems [16]. The authors of A Framework for Mathematics Curricula in Engineering Education propose that

mathematics should be taught as an integrated subject, and as an applied science because real-life problems can enhance students' deep learning approach [10]. The continuation of this research may focus on the success of the application of the above mentioned strategies. It is our responsibility to set our students on a more productive and satisfying life path.

7 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The research for this paper was financially supported by the EU and the Hungarian Government from the project. Intensification of the activities of HU-MATHS-IN-Hungarian Service Network of Mathematics for Industry and Innovation under grant number EFOP-3.6.2-16-2017-00015.

REFERENCES

- [1] Amelink, C. T., Artis, S., & King Liu, T. J. (2015). Examining the self-efficacy of community college STEM majors: Factors related to four-year degree attainment. *Community College Journal of Research and Practice*, 39(12), 1111-1124.
- [2] Cohen, R., & Kelly, A. M. (2019). The impact of community college science and mathematics coursetaking on graduation, transfer, and non-completion. *The Review of Higher Education*, 42(2), 595-617.
- [3] Carter, M. (2009). Visible learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement.
- [4] Marzano, R. J. (2000). A new era of school reform: Going where the research takes us. Aurora, CO: Midcontinent Research for Education and Learning.
- [5] Lee, J., & Stankov, L. (2018). Non-cognitive predictors of academic achievement: Evidence from TIMSS and PISA. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 65, 50-64.
- [6] Bandura, A. (1977). Self-efficacy: Toward a unifying theory of behavioral change. *Psychological Review*, 84, 191–215.
- [7] Bandura, A. (1997). *Self-efficacy: The exercise of control*. New York: Freeman.
- [8] Hutchison, M. A., Follman, D. K., Sumpter, M., & Bodner, G. M. (2006). Factors influencing the self-efficacy beliefs of first-year engineering students. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 95(1), 39-47.
- [9] Biggs, J.B. (1987). *Student approaches to studying and learning*. Camberwell, Vic. : Australian Council for Educational Research, Melbourne.
- [10] A Framework for Mathematics Curricula in Engineering Education (2013), European Society for Engineering Education, Brussels, <http://sefi.htw-aalen.de/curriculum/competency%20based%20curriculum%20incl%20ads.pdf>
- [11] Usher, E. L., & Pajares, F. (2009). Sources of self-efficacy in mathematics: A validation study. *Contemporary educational psychology*, 34(1), 89-101.
- [12] Hussin, F., Hamed, S., & Jam, S. M. (2017). Approaches to learning of engineering students: deep or surface. *Int Acad Res J Soc Sci*, 3(1), 122-127.

- [13] Verešová, M., & Foglová, L. (2018). Academic Self-Efficacy, Approach to Learning and Academic Achievement. *Health and Academic Achievement*, 177.
- [14] Honicke, T., & Broadbent, J. (2016). The Relation of Academic Self-Efficacy to University Student Academic Performance: A Systematic Review. *Educational Research Review*, 17, 63-84.
- [15] Margolis, H., & McCabe, P. P. (2006). Improving self-efficacy and motivation: What to do, what to say. *Intervention in school and clinic*, 41(4), 218-227.
- [16] Dolmans, D. H., Loyens, S. M., Marcq, H., & Gijbels, D. (2016). Deep and surface learning in problem-based learning: a review of the literature. *Advances in health sciences education*, 21(5), 1087-1112.